

The Influence Of Brand Love And Brand Trust On Repurchase Intention Through Consumer Satisfaction Of Indomie Products In Pekanbaru City

Nurul Fadilla Kennedy

Riau University, Pekanbaru, Indonesia

*Email : nurul.fadilla2700@student.unri.ac.id

Gatot Wijayanto

Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Riau University, Pekanbaru, Indonesia

Email : gatot.wijayanto@lecturer.unri.ac.id

Aida Nursanti

Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Riau University, Pekanbaru, Indonesia

Email : aidanursanti1601@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO :

Keywords :

Brand Love;
Brand Trust;
Repurchase Intention;
Consumer Satisfaction

Article History :

Received :2024-03-11
Revised : 2024-05-18
Accepted :2024-06-01
Online :2024-06-12

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the effect of Brand Love and Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction of Indomie products in Pekanbaru City. The population in this study are consumers who know and have bought Indomie products. In sampling using nonprobability sampling with purposive sampling technique so that a sample of 114 respondents was obtained. The data analysis method uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the SmartPLS version 4 program. The results showed that Brand Love and Brand Trust affect the Consumer Satisfaction of Indomie products in Pekanbaru City. Brand Love and Brand Trust affect Repurchase Intention in Indomie products in Pekanbaru City. Consumer Satisfaction affects Repurchase Intention in Indomie products in Pekanbaru City. Brand Love and Brand Trust affect Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction of Indomie products in Pekanbaru City.

INTRODUCTION

Lifestyle changes supported by the globalization era affect people's consumption patterns. Changes in consumption patterns are influenced by fast-paced and instant developments. As it is today, many people live a practical life, especially in terms of consumption for daily life. It is also not surprising that many instant food products are present in the community, considering that Indonesian people like something practical. This is so that they can shorten the time needed to balance their busy lives and activities that require a lot of time. One of the most popular fast food is instant noodles. Instant noodles are considered a flexible, practical and cheap dish, as well as easy to process and requires little time in the serving process.

The high consumption of instant noodles has increased competition between instant noodle companies. It is proven that the existence of various instant noodle brands on the market can encourage companies to compete for potential customers. The diversity of instant noodle products encourages potential consumers to select and identify before making a purchase. Those who have completed the selection and identification process will choose a brand that they believe matches their tastes and criteria.

According to the data from the Top Brand Award in 2023, the instant noodle brand Indomie ranks first as the best brand of consumer choice. As an instant noodle brand that has long been recognized by the Indonesian people, Indomie has been popular and has a name in the hearts of the Indonesian people.

Several studies reveal that Brand Love and Brand Trust are very important in a product. Because the existence of high Brand Love and Brand Trust allows consumers to stay with the product brand they are currently using because they already trust and like it. Consumers who already have a sense of love for the brand they like will give their trust to the brand.

Brand Love in products is a type of emotional satisfaction based on their experience with certain brands (Winarto & Widyastuti, 2021). The application of Brand Love in a product allows consumers to foster a sense of love for a brand, so that consumers have a desire to own the brand. The feeling of consumer love for a brand influences consumers in recommending their beloved brands to other consumers.

Brand Trust can provide an effective role in increasing the tendency of consumer behavior and can influence the tendency of consumer behavior towards a brand (Rahmanda & Farida, 2021). Consumers will definitely give trust to a brand that they love, and will tend to have a buying interest in the products of the brand in question, it is not impossible that these consumers will make repeat purchases of a product brand that they like.

The success of a business depends on its ability to satisfy its customers. A company's ability to satisfy its consumers can help it compete with competitors. A company will gain a competitive advantage and become invincible in the business world if it can keep its consumers happy. Consumers who are happy with a company's products or services will generally be ready to spend more money on them, then buy the products or services more often, and of course they will remain loyal to the company.

A consumer makes a repeat purchase by repeating the purchase of a brand and using it on an ongoing basis. Meanwhile, the satisfaction obtained by consumers can encourage repeat purchases. By looking in terms of love and good trust, it will give a good impression to a brand. So it is very reasonable to say that Brand Love and Brand Trust can affect Consumer Satisfaction in making repeat purchases.

LITERATURE RESEARCH

A. Consumer Behavior

Successful marketing requires companies to be in full contact with their consumers. Kotler and Keller (2009) suggest Consumer Behavior as the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and how goods, services, ideas, or experiences satisfy their needs and wants.

B. Brand

The American Marketing Association in Kotler and Keller (2009) defines a brand as a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination thereof, which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiate them from competitors.

C. Brand Love

Brand Love is an attitude of consumers who have an interest in a brand so that they can provide positive assessments and emotions towards the brand by recognizing the brand as a good brand. This can declare consumer love for the brand.

Brand Love is an integrated part of consumer self-expression by using a certain brand and displaying their love for that brand (Albert & Merunka, 2013). Brand Love is the attitude of consumers who have reached the stage of emotional attraction because they feel satisfied with a particular brand (Carroll & Ahuvia in Rahayu, 2020).

Brand Love is a feeling of love that grows when consumers have a deeper attraction to a brand compared to competing brands (Kusuma, et. al., 2020). Every consumer who is attached to a brand often feels the need and desire to own high-quality products because of their love for the brand. As a result, every time a company releases a new product whose previous product was well received, consumers quickly decide to buy the new item.

D. Brand Trust

Brand Trust is a consumer's perception of a brand that can satisfy needs and guarantee consumer value for the brand so that a feeling of security arises when consumers use it. This can realize the willingness of consumers to trust a brand.

Trust in the brand can lead to purchases because it is considered that the products of the brand are safe when used. When the brand has previously been liked and loved by consumers, the level of consumer trust in the brand is getting bigger. Fandiyanto & Kurniawan (2019) state that trust involves a person's willingness to behave in a certain way because of the belief that his partner will provide the expected satisfaction and an expectation that someone generally has that another person's word, promise, or statement can be trusted.

Brand Trust as the average consumer's willingness to rely on the brand's ability to perform the specified function (Sitorus, et. al., 2022). Brand Trust is the perception of reliability from the consumer's point of view based on experience or more on a sequence of transactions or interactions characterized by fulfilling expectations of product performance and satisfaction (Ferrinadewi, 2018; in Syamsuddinnor, et. al., 2021).

E. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase Intention is a consumer attitude in terms of taking an initiative to buy the same product for the second time or even beyond. Repurchase Intention is a purchase interest based on the purchase experience that has been made. High Repurchase Intention reflects the high level of satisfaction of consumers when deciding to adopt a product. The decision to adopt or reject a product arises after consumers try the product and then a feeling of liking or disliking the product arises. A sense of liking for the product arises if consumers have the perception that the products they use are of good quality and can meet or even exceed consumer desires and expectations (Sartika, 2017).

Repurchase Intention is a purchase intention based on purchasing experiences that have been made in the past (Hasan, 2018). Repurchase Intention is defined as the desire and action of consumers to repurchase a product, because of the satisfaction received in accordance with what is desired from a product (Nurhayati, 2012; in Alfaini, et. al., 2022).

F. Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is a consumer assessment response to a product or service by comparing initial expectations with expectations which will shape the level of a person's feelings whether they will feel satisfied and happy or vice versa.

Consumer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the perception of the performance (results) of a product with his expectations (Tjiptono, 2015). Customer Satisfaction as the level of a person's feelings after feeling satisfaction with the value provided by a product or service, with a high probability of becoming a customer for a long time (Hasibuan, et. al., 2021).

G. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Navarone & Evanita (2019)

H. Hypothesis

- H1. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Consumer Satisfaction.
- H2. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Customer Satisfaction.
- H3. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Repurchase Intention.
- H4. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention.
- H5. It is suspected that there is an influence between Consumer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention.
- H6. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction.
- H7. It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction.

METHOD

This research was conducted in 2023 to 2024 with a sample of people aged 17 years and over who live in Pekanbaru City. The sampling method used is non-probability sampling, specifically using purposive sampling. Respondents were selected purposively from individuals who knew and had bought Indomie brand instant noodle products. The respondents obtained totaled 114 people and were given questions with a total of 15 statements. The results obtained were analyzed through the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) method, utilizing SmartPLS 4 software.

SEM-PLS can perform analysis in one test and explain the relationship between variables. PLS is used to assist researchers in supporting theory and explaining whether there is a relationship between latent variables or not. The PLS method is able to describe latent variables (not directly measured) and measured using indicators (Ghozali, 2008). The selection of SEM-PLS because this research has latent variables that can be measured based on indicators so that the author can analyze with clear and detailed calculations. The variables used in this study are described as follows:

Table 1. Variable Operational Definition

Variables	Definition	Indicator	Scale
Brand Love (X1)	Brand Love is a feeling of love that grows when consumers have a deeper attraction to a brand than competing brands.	1. Recognize the brand as a very good brand 2. Have an interest in the brand 3. Have a positive assessment of the brand 4. Having positive emotions in response to the brand 5. Declaration of love for the brand	Likert
	Kusuma, et. al., (2020)	Albert & Merunka (2013)	
Brand Trust (X2)	Brand Trust is defined as the average consumer's willingness to rely on a brand's ability to perform a specified function.	1. Trust 2. Reliable 3. Honest 4. Security	Likert
	Sitorus, et. al., (2022)	Chauduri & Holbrook (2001)	
Repurchase Intention (Y)	Repurchase Intention is a purchase intention based on purchasing experiences that have been made in the past.	1. The need for the product 2. Desire to repurchase 3. Interest in continuing to use	Likert
	Hasan (2018)	Ferdinand (2006)	

Variables	Definition	Indicator	Scale
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	Consumer Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the perception of the performance (results) of a product with its expectations. Tjiptono (2015)	1. Fulfilled expectations 2. Loyal attitude 3. Willingness to recommend Tjiptono (2012)	Likert

Source: Processed Data (2023)

The tests carried out in this study are measurement model testing (outer model) and structural model testing (inner model). Outer model testing in this study was tested with validity and reliability tests. The validity assessment consists of testing convergent validity (Loading Factor, Average Variance Extracted) and discriminant validity (Cross Loading, Fornell-Larcker). Simultaneously, the reliability assessment involves the evaluation of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha. These checks are based on (Hair et al., 2014). Meanwhile, the inner model test consists of the R-square test and the Model Fit test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Evaluation of the Measurement Model or Outer Model

a. Validity Testing

1) Convergent Validity Test

Table 2. Loading Factor

Variables	Loading Factor	Description
Brand Love (X1)		
X1.1	0.742	Valid
X1.2	0.734	Valid
X1.3	0.742	Valid
X1.4	0.668	Valid
X1.5	0.731	Valid
Brand Trust (X2)		
X2.1	0.767	Valid
X2.2	0.769	Valid
X2.3	0.772	Valid
X2.4	0.744	Valid
Repurchase Intention (Y)		
Y1	0.782	Valid
Y2	0.839	Valid
Y3	0.761	Valid
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)		
Z1	0.806	Valid
Z2	0.715	Valid
Z3	0.851	Valid

Source: Processed Data, 2024

From Table 2, it can be seen that the indicators of each convergent validity value meet the predetermined criteria, namely all above 0.6.

Table 3. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE	Description
Brand Love (X1)	0.524	Valid
Brand Trust (X2)	0.582	Valid
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	0.628	Valid
Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.631	Valid

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on Table 3 above is one of the convergent validity by looking at the AVE value. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct is greater than 0.5. It can be seen that the four constructs have met convergent validity. Brand Love has a value of $0.524 > 0.50$, Brand Trust has a value of $0.582 > 0.50$, Consumer Satisfaction has a value of $0.628 > 0.50$, and Repurchase Intention has a value of $0.631 > 0.50$.

2) Discriminant Validity

Table 4. Discriminant Validity - Cross Loading

Indicator	Brand Love (X1)	Brand Trust (X2)	Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	Repurchase Intention (Y)
X1.1	0.742	0.475	0.486	0.508
X1.2	0.734	0.440	0.534	0.358
X1.3	0.742	0.411	0.480	0.358
X1.4	0.668	0.249	0.422	0.440
X1.5	0.731	0.397	0.450	0.500
X2.1	0.504	0.767	0.492	0.497
X2.2	0.335	0.769	0.407	0.401
X2.3	0.454	0.772	0.569	0.418
X2.4	0.355	0.744	0.457	0.351
Y1	0.454	0.488	0.415	0.782
Y2	0.521	0.444	0.545	0.839
Y3	0.455	0.382	0.478	0.761
Z1	0.571	0.498	0.806	0.400
Z2	0.432	0.381	0.715	0.502
Z3	0.551	0.614	0.851	0.535

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the data from Table 4, it can be seen that all indicators have met discriminant validity. The Brand Love variable has 5 indicators which are denoted by X1.1 to X1.5. The X1.1 indicator has a loading value of 0.742, which is greater than the loading value to other constructs, namely 0.475, 0.486, 0.508. For other indicators, it is also the same, which has a loading value that is greater than the loading value to other constructs.

The Brand Trust variable has 4 indicators which are denoted by X2.1 to X2.4. The X2.1 indicator has a loading value of 0.767, which is greater than the loading value to other constructs, namely 0.504, 0.492, 0.497. For other indicators, it is also the same, which has a loading value that is greater than the loading value of other constructs.

The Repurchase Intention variable has 3 indicators which are denoted by Y1 to Y3. The Y1 indicator has a loading value of 0.782 where the loading value is greater than the loading value to other constructs, namely 0.454, 0.488, 0.415. For other indicators, it is also the same, which has a loading value that is greater than the loading value to other constructs.

The Consumer Satisfaction variable has 3 indicators which are denoted by Z1 to Z3. Indicator Z1 has a loading value of 0.806 where the loading value is greater than the loading value to other constructs, namely 0.571, 0.498, 0.400. For other indicators, it is also the same, which has a loading value that is greater than the loading value to other constructs.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity - Fornell-Larcker

Variables	Brand Love (X1)	Brand Trust (X2)	Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	Repurchase Intention (Y)
Brand Love (X1)	0.724			
Brand Trust (X2)	0.548	0.763		
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	0.656	0.637	0.793	
Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.602	0.551	0.606	0.795

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on Table 5 above, it can be seen that the correlation value of variables with other variables has a greater value, so it can be concluded that discriminant validity testing has been fulfilled.

b. Reliability Testing

Table 6. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Brand Love (X1)	0.773	0.846
Brand Trust (X2)	0.762	0.848
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	0.702	0.835
Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.707	0.837

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on Table 6, data that has composite reliability > 0.70 can be declared to have a high reliability value. Data that has a Cronbach's alpha value can be declared reliable if > 0.70 for all constructs. Based on the results of the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha above, it can be concluded that all variables have met the composite reliability criteria.

Figure 2. Model 1

Source: Processed Data, 2024

2. Evaluation of Structural Model or Inner Model

a. R-square test

Table 7. R-square

Variables	R-square	R-Square Adjusted
Consumer Satisfaction (Z)	0.540	0.531
Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.465	0.451

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the output results from Table 7 above, it shows that the R-Square value of the Brand Love (X1) and Brand Trust (X2) variables on Consumer Satisfaction (Z) is 0.540 and is included in the moderate model category. These results indicate that 54% of the Consumer Satisfaction variable is influenced by the Brand Love and Brand Trust variables, the rest is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

Meanwhile, the R-square value for the influence of the Brand Love (X1) and Brand Trust (X2) variables on Repurchase Intention (Y) has an effect of 0.465 and is included in the weak category. This shows that 46.5% of the Repurchase Intention variable is influenced by the variables Brand Love, Brand Trust, and Customer Satisfaction, the rest is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

b. Model Fit test

Table 8. Model Fit

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.088	0.088
NFI	0.691	0.691

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on table 8 above, it can be concluded that the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square) value of 0.088 <0.10 and the NFI value of 0.691 is almost close to 1. So it can be said that the model has met the requirements of the fit model.

c. Hypothesis Testing

This hypothesis testing aims to prove the truth of the research conjecture or hypothesis. The significance level used in this study is 5%. So that as a basis for decision making if the p-value <0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted, if the p-value > 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected.

Figure 3. Model 2

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing Results (Direct Effect)

Table with 5 columns: Variables, Path Coefficients, T statistics, P values, Description. It lists direct effects from Brand Love (X1) and Brand Trust (X2) to Consumer Satisfaction (Z) and Repurchase Intention (Y), and from Consumer Satisfaction (Z) to Repurchase Intention (Y).

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Table 10. Hypothesis Testing Results (Indirect Effect)

Variables	Path Coefficients	T statistics	P values	Description
Brand Love (X1) -> Consumer Satisfaction (Z) -> Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.118	2.039	0.042	Accepted
Brand Trust (X2) -> Consumer Satisfaction (Z) -> Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.106	2.213	0.027	Accepted

Source: Processed Data, 2024

DISCUSSION

1. The Effect of Brand Love on Consumer Satisfaction

H1 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on the table, it can be seen that the Brand Love variable has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.438 and a t-statistic value (5.883 > 1.96) with a p-value (0.000 < 0.05). This figure shows that the better the Brand Love of a product, it can increase Customer Satisfaction by 43.8%, which means that Brand Love positively and significantly affects Customer Satisfaction and serves as a foundation for fostering sustainable loyalty and improving the overall brand experience. This shows that Brand Love has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, so Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Brand Love can influence Consumer Satisfaction by fostering a deep emotional connection between consumers and brands. When consumers feel Brand Love, they tend to have a stronger relationship with the brand. Consumers who have a sense of love for a brand are more likely to feel satisfied with the products they buy from that brand. This is due to a strong emotional attachment, which makes consumers more tolerant of shortcomings and more motivated to seek products from the same brand in the future.

2. The Effect of Brand Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

H2 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Customer Satisfaction

Based on Table it can be seen that the Brand Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.396 and a t-statistic value (5.541 > 1.96) with a p-value (0.000 < 0.05). This figure shows that the better the Brand Trust, the more it can increase Customer Satisfaction by 39.6%, which means that Brand Trust plays an important role in Customer Satisfaction, because Brand Trust fosters confidence, reliability, and assurance in brand offerings, and ultimately leads to higher levels of satisfaction and loyalty among consumers. This shows that Brand Trust has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, so Hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Brand Trust plays an important role in shaping Consumer Satisfaction, because Brand Trust forms the foundation of reliability, credibility and consistency in brand offerings. Brand Trust forms the basis of long-term relationships between brands and consumers. Consumers who have strong trust in a brand tend to be loyal to that brand. In addition, Brand Trust can help brands face competition in the market, because consumers prefer brands they trust over unknown brands.

3. The Effect of Brand Love on Repurchase Intention

H3 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Repurchase Intention

Based on Table it can be seen that the Brand Love variable has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention with a path coefficient of 0.311 and a t-statistic value (3.495 > 1.96) with a p-value (0.000 < 0.05). This figure shows that if you have good Brand Love, then Repurchase Intention will increase by 31.1%, which means that Brand Love significantly affects Repurchase Intention, because this creates a strong emotional bond and affinity for the brand, which results in a greater likelihood for consumers to repeatedly choose and buy from that brand than competitors. This shows that Brand Love has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention, so Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

In the marketing world, Brand Love as an emotional connection between brands and consumers can have a significant impact on Repurchase Intention. There are several factors that can influence the formation of Brand Love, such as positive consumer personal experiences, brand values that are in line with consumer

values, effective brand communication, and so on. When consumers feel that the brand provides a satisfying experience, they will become more loyal and choose to repurchase products from the brand.

4. The Effect of Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention

H4 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention

Based on Table it can be seen that the Brand Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention with a path coefficient of 0.210 and a t-statistic value ($2.005 > 1.96$) with a p-value ($0.045 < 0.05$). This figure shows that if you have good Brand Trust, then Repurchase Intention will increase by 21%, which means that the level of Brand Trust has a big impact on Repurchase Intention, because this instills confidence and reliability in consumers, fostering a sense of security that encourages them to choose the brand consistently for future purchases. This shows that Brand Trust has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention, so Hypothesis 4 is accepted.

The influence of Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention is very large, because trust serves as a fundamental pillar in fostering customer loyalty and repeat purchases. Consumer interest in making repurchases is strongly influenced by brand trust. Consumers who have trust in a brand will feel comfortable and confident to repurchase products from that brand. This is largely because long-term relationships between brands and consumers are built on trust.

5. The Effect of Consumer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention

H5 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention

Based on Table it can be seen that the Consumer Satisfaction variable has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention with a path coefficient of 0.268 and a t-statistic value ($2.359 > 1.96$) with a p-value ($0.018 < 0.05$). This figure shows that if Consumer Satisfaction is high, Repurchase Intention will increase by 26.8%, which means that a high level of Consumer Satisfaction often leads to an increase in Repurchase Intention, because satisfied consumers are more likely to develop brand loyalty and repeatedly choose their products over competitors, thereby driving sustainable business success. This shows that Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention, so Hypothesis 5 is accepted.

Customer satisfaction has a significant influence on Repurchase Intention. Consumer satisfaction can build trust. When customers are satisfied with a product, they will have more trust in the brand or company. This trust can encourage them to buy from the same brand or company again. Consumer satisfaction contributes to the establishment of a good brand reputation. Satisfied customers tend to leave positive reviews and recommend products or services to others. Thus, it can be concluded that Customer Satisfaction has a significant influence on Repurchase Intention. Companies that focus on consistently meeting the needs and wants of their customers will tend to benefit from higher customer retention rates and sustainable business growth.

6. The Effect of Brand Love on Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction

H6 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Love on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction.

Based on Table it can be seen that the Brand Love variable has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.118 and a t-statistic value ($2.039 > 1.96$) with a p-value ($0.042 < 0.05$). This figure shows that Brand Love has an influence in increasing Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction by 11.8%, which means that Brand Love positively influences Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction by fostering a strong emotional connection with the brand, which in turn increases overall satisfaction with the brand's products. This higher satisfaction increases the likelihood of consumers making repeat purchases, driven by their deep love and loyalty to the brand. This shows that Brand Love has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction, so Hypothesis 6 is accepted.

The influence of Brand Love on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction is a multi-faceted process that underscores the emotional connection between consumers and brands. Repurchase Intention is often influenced by the emotional attachment or "brand love" that consumers have for a brand, especially when it is triggered by Customer Satisfaction.

7. The Effect of Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction

H7 : It is suspected that there is an influence between Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction.

Based on Table it can be seen that the Brand Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.106 and a t-statistic value ($2.213 > 1.96$) with a p-value ($0.027 < 0.05$). This figure shows that Brand Trust has an influence in increasing Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction by 10.6%, which means that Brand Trust has a positive impact on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction by instilling trust and reliability in brand offerings. When consumers have trust in brands, they tend to be satisfied with their purchases. In the end, it will strengthen their trust and confidence in the brand, which leads to an increase in Repurchase Intention because consumers feel confident that they will continue to receive high quality products. This shows that Brand Trust has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction, so Hypothesis 7 is accepted.

The effect of Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention through Consumer Satisfaction shows the importance of building and maintaining trust with consumers to encourage long-term loyalty and repeat purchases. Brands that prioritize building trust and providing the best experience for consumers are in a superior position to establish close relationships and achieve sustainable growth in a competitive market.

CONCLUSION

Brand Love for Indomie, based on the results of respondents' responses, obtained an overall value that showed a very good category. This indicates that many consumers feel very emotionally attached to Indomie products. They may have consistent positive experiences with Indomie products, feel connected to the values represented by the brand, and may consider Indomie as part of their daily consumption.

Brand Trust in Indomie, based on the results of respondents' responses, obtained an overall value that showed in the good category. This is because the Indomie brand has succeeded in building strong and solid trust among its consumers, although there is still room to continue to improve and strengthen the level of trust.

Repurchase Intention in Indomie, based on the results of respondents' responses, obtained an overall value that showed a good category. This indicates that the majority of consumers who have tried Indomie tend to buy it again in the future. Thus, Indomie has succeeded in building strong consumer loyalty and potential for long-term growth in sales.

Consumer Satisfaction with Indomie, based on the results of respondents' responses, obtained an overall value that showed a good category. This indicates that the majority of consumers are satisfied with Indomie products after trying and consuming them. This reflects that Indomie has succeeded in meeting consumer expectations, so that Indomie can build a good reputation among its consumers.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdillah, W., & Hartono, J. (2015). Partial least square (PLS) Alternatif structural equation modeling (SEM) dalam penelitian bisnis. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi, 22, 103-150.
- Agustin, P. D., Hamdun, E. K., & Syahputra, H. (2023). Pengaruh Word of Mouth Dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Melalui Kepuasan Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Ikan Kering Ud. Putra Putri Di Situbondo. *Jurnal Mahasiswa Entrepreneurship (JME)*, 2(9), 2040. <https://doi.org/10.36841/jme.v2i9.3619>
- Albert, N., & Merunka, D. (2013). The role of brand love in consumer-brand relationships. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 30(3), 258–266. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363761311328928>
- Anjani, A. (2017). Pengaruh Brand Image Dan Brand Trust Terhadap Brand Loyalty Lipstik Revlon (Studi Kasus Konsumen Lipstik Revlon di Yogyakarta). In *Block Caving – A Viable Alternative?* (Vol. 21, Issue 1).
- Artana, I. W. A. (2023). the Influence of Experiential Marketing on Customer Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction As an Intervening Variable for Mahakam Lantern Garden Visitors. *Research Journal Of Management*, 1(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebar.v4i03.1286>
- Awi, Y. L., & Chaipooipirutana, S. (2014). A Study of Factors Affecting Consumer's Repurchase Intention Toward

- XYZ Restaurant, Myanmar. <https://doi.org/10.15242/icehm.ed0814093>
- Bisnis.tempo.co (2023) Sejarah Indomie Mie Instan Nomor Satu di Indonesia. bisnis.tempo.co. Diakses pada 10 Oktober 2023, dari <https://bisnis.tempo.co/read/1770108/sejarah-indomie-mie-instan-nomor-satu-di-indonesia>
- Cermati.com (2023) Sejarah Panjang dan Perjalanan Sukses Indomie. cermati.com. Diakses pada 10 Oktober 2023, dari <https://www.cermati.com/artikel/sejarah-panjang-dan-perjalanan-sukses-indomie>
- Dharmayana, I. M. A., & Rahanatha, G. B. (2017). Pengaruh Brand Equity, Brand Trust, Brand Preference, Dan Kepuasan Konsumen Terhadap Niat Membeli Kembali. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 6(4), 1177–1189. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiab.2021.31528>
- Efendi, M. I., & Farida, S. N. (2021). Pengaruh Brand Loveterhadap Brand Loyaltydan Willingness To Pay Premium Price (Studi Pada Konsumen Starbucks di Kota Surabaya). *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis (EK&BI)*, 4(1), 384–392. <https://doi.org/10.37600/ekbi.v4i1.228>
- Erwindo, E. (2012). Analisis Produksi Mie Instant Pada Pt. Indofood Cabang Pekanbaru (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau).
- Fadiyanto, R., & Kurniawan, R. E. (2019). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Merek Dan Citra Merek Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang “Kopi Toraja” Di Coffee Josh Situbondo. *ECOBUSS : Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 7(1), 21–42.
- Ghozali, Imam. (2008). *Structural Equation Modelling*, Edisi II, Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). Partial least squares konsep, teknik dan aplikasi menggunakan program smartpls 3.0 untuk penelitian empiris. Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP.
- Ghassani, M. T. (2017). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk Dan Harga Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Bandeng Juwana Vaccum Melalui Kepuasan Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Kasus Pada Pelanggan Pt. Bandeng Juwana Elrina Semarang). *Diponegoro Journal Of Social And Political Science Tahun*, 1–8. <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/>
- Giovandhi, L., & Adlina, H. (2023). The Effect of Product Quality and Brand Love on Repurchase Intention on Apple Brand (Study on Generation Z Students Using Apple Products at the University of North Sumatra). *Journal of Economics and Business (JECOMBI)*, 3(02), 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.58471/jecombi.v3i02.46>
- Gómez, M. C. O., & Pérez, W. G. (2018). Effects of Brand Love and Brand Equity on Repurchase Intentions of Young Consumers. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 8(4), 7–13. https://r.search.yahoo.com/_ylt=AwrKDrw7pSNIDHAYS_jLQwx.;_ylu=Y29sbwNzZzMEcG9zAzUEdnRpZAMEc2VjA3Ny/RV=2/RE=1696863676/RO=10/RU=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.researchgate.net%2Fpublication%2F326235160_Effects_Of_Brand_Love_And_Brand_Equity_On_Repurchase_Intentions_Of_
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. American : SAGE Publications, Inc. California, USA.
- Hasan, Ali. (2018). *Marketing dan Kasus-Kasus Pilihan*. Yogyakarta. CAPS (Center For Academic Publishing Service).
- Hasibuan, R. M., Dr. Fitriani Harahap, S.Pd., M., & Armansyah Lubis, S.E., M. . (2021). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Di Cafe Vanilla Panyabungan. *Jurnal Misi Institut Pendidikan Tapanuli Selatan (IPTS)*, 4(3), 175–182.
- Hayuni, H. Z., & Sharif, O. O. (2023). The Effects Of Brand Image , Brand Satisfaction , And Brand Trust On Loyalty Formation : The Moderation Role Of Brand Love And Brand Respect Of Mixue Ice Moderation Role of Brand Love and Brand Respect of Mixue Ice Cream & Tea . 12(04), 642–658.
- Indomie.co.id (2011). Indomie. indomie.Co.Id. Diakses pada 06 Juni 2023, dari <https://www.indomie.co.id/>
- Indofood.com (2023). Indofood. indofood.com. Diakses pada 10 Oktober 2023, dari <https://www.indofood.com/>
- Indofoodcbp.com (2023). Indofood. indofoodcbp.com. Diakses pada 10 Oktober 2023, dari <https://www.indofoodcbp.com/>
- Indrasari, D. M. (2019). *Pemasaran & Kepuasan Pelanggan*. Unitomo Press. Surabaya
- Kamilla, W. F., & Bestari, D. K. P. (2022). Pengaruh Popularitas Nct Dream sebagai Brand Ambassador dan Kepuasan Konsumen terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Mie Lemonilo (Studi pada Masyarakat di Kota Bandung). *JIIIP - Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan*, 5(9), 3701–3708. <https://doi.org/10.54371/jiip.v5i9.855>

- Kholifah, U., Kusnadi, E., & Fandiyanto, R. (2022). Pengaruh Keragaman Produk Dan Endorser Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Pada Cafe D'poto Situbondo Dengan Minat Beli Sebagai Variabel Intervening. 1(4), 1–23.
- Kompas.com (2023, 19 Februari). 50 Tahun Sejarah Indomie dan Kekayaan Pemilikinya. Kompas.Com. Diakses pada 06 Juni 2023, dari <https://www.kompas.com/tren/read/2023/02/19/150000265/50-tahun-sejarah-indomie-dan-kekayaan-pemilikinya?page=all>.
- Kotler, Philip dan Kevin Lane Keller. (2009). Manajemen Pemasaran. Penerjemah B. Molan. Edisi Ketigabelas. Jilid 1. Jakarta: Indeks Kelompok Gramedia.
- Kotler dan Keller. (2016). Manajemen Pemasaran. Jilid I. Edisi ke 13. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Kusuma, A. H. P., Sudirman, A., Purnomo, A., Aisyah, S., Sahir, S. H., Rumondang, A., ... & Simarmata, J. (2020). Brand Management: Esensi, Posisi & Strategi. Yayasan Kita Menulis. Medan.
- Lestari, R., & Elwisam. (2019). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga, Kualitas Produk, dan Citra Merek Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen dan Dampaknya Pada Minat Beli Ulang Produk Mie Instant Sedaap. Jurnal Ilmu Dan Budaya, 41(63), 7495–7520.
- Mansyur, M., Asiyah, S., & Millaningtyas, R. (2021). Pengaruh Brand Image, Brand Love, Brand Trust dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Sepatu Vans Di Malang (Studi Pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Islam Malang Jurusan Manajemen Angkatan 2018). E-Jurnal Riset Manajemen, 87–100. www.fe.unisma.ac.id
- Maulana, F. G., Wibowo, L. A., & Widjajanta, B. (2018). Gambaran Brand Identification Dan Brand Loves Pada Pengguna Forum Jual Beli Kaskus Di Kota Bandung. Journal of Business Management Education, 3(3), 14–24.
- Maydona, R., Arief, M. Y., & Harisandi, Y. (2022). Pengaruh Harga Dan Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Melalui Minat Beli Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Cafe Anak Pantai Di Cermee Bondowoso. 1(6), 1234–1248.
- Murtaza, Z. D., & Bambang. (2022). Pengaruh Brand Awareness, Brand Love dan Brand Trust terhadap Purchase Decision Kopi Spesial Arabica UD. Kupu Pantan Raya Kabupaten Aceh Tengah. Jurnal Pemasaran Kompetitif, 5(3), 341–355. <http://www.openjournal.unpam.ac.id/index.php/JPK>
- Navarone, N., & Evanita, S. (2019). Pengaruh Service Quality Dan Brand Trust Terhadap Repurchase Intention Melalui Customer Satisfaction Sebagai Mediasi Pada Produk Smartphone Samsung Di Kalangan Mahasiswa Kota Padang. Jurnal Kajian Manajemen Dan Wirausaha, 01, 50–62.
- Puspita, R. C., & Suryoko, S. (2017). Pengaruh Iklan, Harga, Dan Kepercayaan Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Kosmetik Revlon (Studi Pada Mahasiswa S1 Universitas Diponegoro). Diponegoro Journal Of Social And Political, 6(3), 418–425. <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/>
- Putri, N. A., Arifin, Z., & Wilopo. (2016). Pengaruh Citra Merek, Kepercayaan Merek, dan Switching Barriers terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan dan Dampaknya pada Loyalitas Pelanggan (Survei Pada Mahasiswa S1 Jurusan Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis Fakultas Ilmu Administrasi Universitas Brawijaya Tahun 2014 / 201. Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB), 32(1), 128–134.
- Rahayu, D. M. (2020). The Effect Of E-Wom And Brand Love On The Purchasing Decisions In Online Shopping. Jurnal Ilmiah Publipreneur, 8(2), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.46961/jip.v8i2.159>
- Sallam, M. A. (2014). The Effects of Brand Image and Brand Identification on Brand Love and Purchase Decision Making: The Role of WOM. International Business Research, 7(10), 187–193. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v7n10p187>
- Santoso, T. A., & Mardian, I. (2020). Pengaruh Brand Image Dan Brand Trust Terhadap Minat Beli Pada Produk Avocado Mantul. Ekonomi & Bisnis, 19(1), 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.32722/eb.v19i1.2789>
- Sartika, D. (2017). Analisis Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Minat Beli Ulang Produk You C 1000 Serta Dampaknya Terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen. Jurnal Penelitian Ekonomi Dan Bisnis, 2(1), 10–21. <http://www.jpheb.dinus.ac.id>
- Sarwono, J. (2010). Pengertian Dasar Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis Ukrida, 10(3), 98528.
- Sitorus, S. A., Romli, N. A., Tingga, C. P., Sukanteri, N. P., Putri, S. E., Gheta, A. P. K., Wardhana, A., Nugraha, K. S. W., Hendrayani, E., Susanto, P. C., Primasanti, Y., & Ulfah, M. (2022). Brand Marketing: The Art Or Branding. In Brand Marketing: the Art of Branding.

- Surti, I., & Anggraeni, F. N. (2020). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen. *Revue: Lentera Bisnis Manajemen*, 3(03), 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.59422/lbm.v2i01.162>
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif*. CV Alfabeta. Bandung
- Suwito, J. (2018). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Pada Cv Global Ac Banjarbaru. 112, 282.
- Syamsuddinnor, Yasrie, A., & Rahman, A. (2021). Analisis Pengaruh Brand Image, Brand Trust Dan Brand Affect Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Air Minum Dalam Kemasan Cleo Pure Water Di Kota Banjarmasin (Studi Pada Konsumen Di Kecamatan Banjamasin Utara Dan Banjarmasin Barat). *Seminar Nasional Sistem Informasi (SENASIF)*, 5(1), 2769–2780. <https://jurnalfti.unmer.ac.id/index.php/senasif/article/download/361/313>
- Syariahsaham.id (2024) PT Indofood CBP Sukses Makmur Tbk (ICBP) Profil. *syariahsaham.id*. Diakses pada 30 April 2024, dari <https://syariahsaham.id/amp/pt-indofood-cbp-sukses-makmur-tbk-icbp>
- Syarifuddin, Mandey, S. L., Tumbuan, W. J. F. A., & Maramis, J. B. (2022). The Effect Of Halal Certificate Trust, Brand Love, Food Quality, On Consumer Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction At Halal Restaurants In North Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(10), 3155–3173.
- Tjiptono, F. (2014). *Pemasaran Jasa: Prinsip, Penerapan dan Penelitian*. Yogyakarta:
- Tjiptono, F. (2015). *Strategi Pemasaran : Edisi 4*. Yogyakarta: ANDI.
- Topbrand-award.com (2023). Top Brand Award. Diakses pada 06 Juni 2023, dari https://www.topbrand-award.com/komparasi_brand/bandingkan?id_award=1&id_kategori=2&id_subkategori=30
- Wardhana, A., Darmadi, A. K., & Sunara, T. A. (2023). the Influence of Brq and Brand Love on Repurchase Intention and Wom in Local Food. *JMBI UNSRAT (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis Dan Inovasi Universitas Sam Ratulangi)*, 10(1), 561–568. <https://doi.org/10.35794/jmbi.v10i1.47677>
- Washil, M. Z., Afandi, M. F., & Sumani. (2023). Pengaruh Pengalaman Konsumen Dan Label Halal Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Melalui Kepuasan Konsumen (Studi Pada Konsumen Mixue Di Kabupaten Jember). *Debt To Equity Ratio, Price Earning Ratio, Current Ratio, Harga Saham Perusahaan Sub Sektor Telekomunikasi*, 3(1), 43–50. jurnal.umj.ac.id/index.php/JMMB
- Winarto, M. R. A., & Widyastuti. (2021). Pengaruh Brand Image dan Brand Love Terhadap Repurchase Intention (Studi Kasus pada Konsumen Produk Gucci di Surabaya). *Nomicpedia : Journal of Economics and Business Innovation*, 1(2), 102–110. <https://journal.inspirasi.or.id/nomicpedia/article/view/65>
- Yeo, S. F., Tan, C. L., Teo, S. L., & Tan, K. H. (2021). The role of food apps servitization on repurchase intention: A study of FoodPanda. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108063>

